

Attention-Based Temporal Resolution Enhancement for Microsleep Forecasting Across Multiple Horizons

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Abstract. Detecting microsleep events, that is, brief involuntary lapses in attention, is critical for safety in tasks such as driving and industrial control. Current EEG-based methods achieve high accuracy (AUC-ROC ≈ 0.95) when detecting microsleep onset in real-time but show reduced predictive sensitivity (17–35% drop) when forecasting events 1–2 seconds ahead, primarily due to diminished temporal resolution of EEG signals. Prediction ahead of microsleep episodes is desirable for utility in operator assessment scenarios.

To address this challenge, we propose an attention-augmented temporal modeling approach that applies a causal multi-head self-attention mechanism before a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network to preserve fine-grained temporal features. In addition, we incorporate a focal loss function to emphasize minority-class microsleep events and mitigate class imbalance.

Experiments on the multi-channel MWT dataset demonstrated consistent and statistically significant improvements over both CSP+SBL and conventional GRU baselines, with sensitivity gains of up to 42 percentage points and AUC-ROC improvements of up to 22 points (Wilcoxon test, $p = 0.0003$). An ablation study confirmed that both focal loss and attention contribute complementary benefits, with their combination yielding the best overall results. To evaluate robustness, we further tested on the single-channel Sleepy Driver dataset, where the proposed model improved specificity and AUC metrics, though gains were more modest than in clinical multi-channel EEG.

Overall, our findings demonstrate that integrating causal attention and focal loss sustains forecasting performance across horizons and datasets, offering a reliable and adaptive framework for real-time microsleep prediction in both clinical and consumer-grade settings.

Keywords: Microsleep forecasting · EEG · Deep Learning · Attention mechanism · GRU · Temporal modeling.

1 Introduction

Driving drowsiness and fatigue-related attention deficiency pose serious safety risks in transportation and healthcare settings. In addition to driving, microsleep forecasting is highly relevant in healthcare, where it can assist in monitoring fatigue in medical professionals during long shifts (for instance, in operating rooms or intensive care units), and support diagnosis and management of patients with sleep disorders or neurological conditions undergoing EEG-based observation. [2] [3]. These domains transportation, healthcare, and industrial control share a common need for early detection of attention lapses, making microsleep forecasting broadly applicable across multiple high stakes environments.

Microsleep events, brief involuntary episodes of sleep lasting 0.5s-15s, often precede critical performance failures. Electroencephalography (EEG) offers a direct window into the neural dynamics underlying vigilance, and many studies have shown high prediction performance for Microsleeps at onset ($\tau = 0s$) [16]. However, the ability to forecast Microsleeps 1s to 2s in advance is far more challenging: forecast performance (especially sensitivity) drops as the prediction horizon increases [16].

The primary reason for this degradation lies in the loss of temporal resolution when aggregating EEG features over longer horizons. As we push τ further from the onset of the event, traditional pipelines tend to blur critical transient patterns, resulting in reduced early warning capability and increased false alarms.

1.1 Gap and Research Question

Despite advances in feature engineering, there remains a fundamental trade-off between the prediction horizon and the temporal fidelity. We pose the following research question.

How can multi-head causal attention improve Microsleep prediction accuracy from EEG, while preserving early warning sensitivity and minimizing false alarms at extended forecast horizons?

1.2 Contributions

To address this question, we make three key contributions:

1. **Replication and Benchmarking:** We reproduce the CSP + SBL pipeline of [16] on our EEG dataset, quantifying its performance at $\tau = 0.25\text{s}$, 0.5s , 0.75s , 1s .
2. **Baseline Recurrent Model:** We implement a vanilla GRU-based forecasting model to establish a deep learning benchmark across these horizons at $\tau = 0\text{s}$, 1s , 2s .
3. **Proposed Attention GRU:** We introduce a causal attention mechanism (before GRU) that adaptively recalibrates temporal features, preserving high sensitivity at $\tau = 1\text{s}$ to 2s and reducing false positives.

1.3 Paper Organization

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews prior work on EEG-based microsleep prediction. Section 3 describes our dataset, preprocessing, and the experimental pipelines and details the evaluation protocol, metrics, and implementation. Sections 4 and 5 present quantitative results and comparative analyses across all horizons. Finally, Section 6 summarizes our findings.

2 Related Work

Microsleep episodes, defined as brief involuntary lapses of consciousness lasting between 0.5–15 seconds, pose serious safety risks in settings such as driving, transportation, and industrial control [4]. A wide range of sensing modalities and machine learning approaches have been investigated for detecting these events. Early work demonstrated that single-channel EEG systems, combined with deep neural networks, can detect microsleeps at the moment of onset ($\tau = 0\text{ s}$) with high accuracy [6]. While appealing for their simplicity, such systems often lack the spatial richness of multi-electrode EEG recordings, which can capture broader neural dynamics.

Multichannel EEG pipelines have therefore been explored to improve robustness, though at the cost of greater complexity and computational demand. Parallel research has examined non-EEG modalities such as speech emotion features [10], image-based facial analysis paired with steering-wheel pressure sensors [13], and video-based eye-aspect-ratio (EAR) monitoring [10] highlighting the potential of multimodal systems. However, direct comparisons against EEG-only forecasting remain limited, and few studies investigate prediction **ahead of time**, which is crucial for real-world intervention systems.

2.1 Feature Extraction

Spectral features (e.g., theta and alpha power) remain a standard approach in microsleep detection. Joint entropy and mutual information features have demonstrated strong discriminative ability (AUCROC = 0.93) [34], although class imbalance limits generalisation. Shoorangiz *et al.* showed that spatio-temporal features extracted via Common Spatial Patterns (CSP) outperform traditional log-power features but degrade substantially as the forecasting horizon increases [16]. Similar effects were observed in blind source extraction methods applied to EEG and EOG signals [15]. Dimensionality reduction techniques such as PCA, PPCA, and nonlinear embeddings have also been explored to manage high-dimensional EEG feature spaces, with varied success [8] [12] ,[11].

Fig. 1: ROC and Precision–Recall curves for the baseline (Vanilla GRU) (top row) and proposed attention-augmented GRU (bottom row) at $\tau = 0$ s.

2.2 Classification and Forecasting Models

A significant proportion of microsleep research focuses on **onset detection** ($\tau = 0$ s). Traditional classifiers (e.g., SVM) and modern CNN architectures have reported strong performance on instantaneous detection tasks [30], though typically with limited analysis of temporal dependencies or forecasting capability. Recurrent models such as LSTMs have been employed to detect behavioural lapses from spectral features [18], but most studies do not extend evaluation beyond the onset.

One of the few investigations into multi-horizon forecasting was conducted by Shoorangiz *et al.* [16], who examined prediction horizons of $\tau = 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0$ s using CSP-based features and sparse Bayesian logistic regression (SBL). Their findings show a sharp decline in sensitivity as τ increases, driven largely by loss of temporal resolution when EEG features are aggregated across longer windows. This degradation underscores the need for forecasting models that preserve fine-grained temporal information.

Recently, attention mechanisms have gained traction in EEG classification tasks, primarily to capture spatial channel relationships or emphasize discriminative spectral features. However, their application to **forecasting** microsleeps ahead of time remains scarcely explored. Unlike prior methods, our work integrates a causal multi-head self-attention module before a GRU backbone, allowing the model to recalibrate temporal features while preventing future data leakage. To the best of our knowledge, this represents one of the first attempts to use causal attention explicitly to enhance temporal resolution for microsleep forecasting across multiple horizons.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset

The utilization of publicly available datasets in microsleep research is notably rare. This study utilizes the Maintenance of Wakefulness Test (MWT) dataset [35], which includes EEG and EOG recordings obtained from a cohort of 76 patients, comprising 50 males with a mean age of 45.6 years (ranging from 18 to 81.3 years). The MWT dataset is structured into four daily trials, divided into two sessions before and after lunch, each separated by at least two hours. All recorded signals within this dataset are bandpass filtered within the 0.5–45 Hz frequency range to ensure data quality and relevance to the study objectives. This dataset is labeled for three states: Awake, Microsleep, and Drowsiness.

For this study, any state labeled as Microsleep was treated as a positive class (MSE), and Awake was treated as the negative class (non-MSE). After windowing the EEG recordings into 1-second non-overlapping segments, the final labeled dataset consisted of 60,548 wakefulness samples and 37,456 microsleep samples, providing a realistic setting for model training and evaluation.

Sleepy Driver EEG Brainwave Dataset

In addition to the MWT dataset, we also evaluated our models on the *Sleepy Driver EEG Brainwave Dataset* [14]. This dataset was collected from four drivers using the NeuroSky MindWave headset, a single-channel consumer-grade EEG device. Each subject completed approximately 5–8 minutes of recordings in both awake and drowsy states, yielding labeled segments for binary classification (sleepy vs. not sleepy). Signals were sampled at approximately one-second intervals and represent power spectral density values ($\mu V^2/Hz$) from a single frontal lobe electrode, with ground and reference electrodes attached to the earlobes.

In both datasets, the “Drowsiness” class was merged with the Awake class to form a unified non-microsleep label. This decision follows prior microsleep forecasting literature, where the primary objective is detecting the transition into microsleep rather than distinguishing intermediate vigilance states. Including drowsiness as a separate class would substantially increase imbalance and reduce interpretability, whereas merging ensures a consistent binary formulation (Microsleep vs. Non-Microsleep) across datasets.

3.2 Baseline Replication: CSP + SBL

We first reproduce the pipeline of [34] on our dataset. Multi-channel EEG is band pass filtered (0.5–30 Hz) and segmented into 1s epochs, with labels defined at forecast horizons $\tau \in \{0.25s, 0.5s, 0.75s, 1s\}$ ahead, and spatially filtered via Common Spatial Patterns (CSP) to yield C components. The log-variance of each component forms a feature vector $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^C$, which is classified by Sparse Bayesian Logistic regression (SBL). Hyperparameters are tuned via 5-fold cross-validation.

3.3 GRU-Only Forecasting

Using the same preprocessed windows, we extract a feature vector at each time-step, forming $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$. A two layer GRU processes \mathbf{X} and outputs hidden states \mathbf{h}_t . The final state \mathbf{h}_T is passed through a dense layer with sigmoid activation to predict the probability of a forthcoming microsleep.

Additionally, a recent study [11] evaluated various classifiers for microsleep detection and found that LSTM-based models achieved strong performance. Inspired by this, we adopted GRU due to its temporal modeling capability and lower computational complexity, making it suitable for efficient forecasting.

3.4 Proposed Attention-Enhanced GRU

To preserve fine-grained temporal cues when increasing τ , we introduce a causal multi-head self-attention layer *before* the GRU. Given \mathbf{X} , we compute

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}} + \mathbf{M}\right) \mathbf{V}, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2: Full pipeline: causal multi-head self-attention is applied before the GRU to enrich temporal feature representations.

where $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{X}W_Q$, $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{X}W_K$, $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{X}W_V$, d_k is the per-head dimension, and \mathbf{M} enforces causality (zeroing future positions). The outputs of H heads are concatenated and linearly projected to yield $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$, which is then input to the same GRU backbone. This pre-GRU attention adaptively recalibrates temporal features, mitigating the blurring of transient patterns at longer horizons.

For both the GRU only baseline and the proposed attention enhanced GRU, each 1s EEG epoch is first converted into a feature sequence $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$, where T denotes the number of time-steps per epoch. Our feature extractor computes:

- $d_{NL} = 5$ nonlinear complexity measures (e.g. sample entropy, spectral entropy, approximate entropy),
- $d_{FD} = 15$ frequency-domain features, namely absolute and relative power in the delta (0.5–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–12 Hz), beta (12–26 Hz) and gamma (26–50 Hz) bands,

all of which have been shown to correlate with microsleep onset [3] [34]. These combined features capture all the shifts that precede Microsleep episodes and serve as the input sequence for the GRU layers.

Furthermore, we adopt the focal loss [1]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{FL} = -\alpha_t(1 - p_t)^\gamma \log(p_t), \quad (2)$$

which down weights easy negatives and focuses training on hard, minority class samples for reducing false alarms in imbalanced Microsleep prediction.

Finally, Unlike standard multi-head attention, our causal attention mechanism applies a temporal mask that prevents each time step from attending to future inputs, ensuring that only current and past EEG segments contribute to the prediction. This preserves the natural temporal flow of information and avoids future data leakage during forecasting.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate models using:

- **Accuracy:** the overall proportion of correctly classified segments, providing a measure of general performance.
- **Sensitivity & Specificity:** these capture true positive and true negative rates for early-warning reliability.
- **Geometric Mean (GM):** $\sqrt{\text{Sens.} \times \text{Spec.}}$, balances performance across both classes.
- **AUC-ROC:** overall discrimination ability.
- **AUC-PR:** robustness to class imbalance and emphasis on the positive (microsleep) class.

These metrics ensure we measure both early warning sensitivity and control of false alarms in an imbalanced and safety-critical forecasting setting.

3.6 Implementation Details

All experiments were implemented in Python 3.8 using PyTorch 1.10 for the GRU and attention models and scikit-learn 0.24 for the CSP+SBL baseline and data splitting. EEG preprocessing (0.5–30 Hz band-pass, 1s windows with 50% overlap) and feature extraction (nonlinear, spectral and temporal features) were performed with NumPy/SciPy. To avoid data leakage, we applied a subject exclusive stratified split (80% train, 20% test) using scikit-learn, preserving the microsleep/non-microsleep class ratios. Deep models were trained with batch size 32, Adam optimizer (initial learning rate 1e-3), two GRU layers (64 128 units), dropout 0.2 and early stopping at validation AUC-ROC (patience = 10). The proposed model adds a 4-head causal multihead self-attention layer (per head dimension 64) before GRU, and uses focal loss to mitigate class imbalance.

3.7 EEG-TCNet Adaptation for Forecasting

EEG-TCNet is a CNN-RNN hybrid architecture initially proposed for EEG-based classification [36]. To investigate its applicability for temporal forecasting, we adapted the architecture to operate on temporally windowed EEG features. The adapted model uses a stack of two-dimensional convolutional layers to capture spatial dependencies across EEG features, followed by a GRU layer for temporal modeling, and a dense output layer for binary classification. Forecasting was performed across $\tau = 0s, 1s,$ and $2s$ horizons. Training and evaluation followed the same protocol as our other baselines.

Table 1: Performance of the GRU baseline VS the proposed attention-augmented model at forecast horizons of 0s 1s and 2s.

Metric	0 s (Onset)		1 s		2 s	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
Train Accuracy	0.72	0.87	0.70	0.84	0.68	0.82
Test Accuracy	0.71	0.85	0.69	0.83	0.67	0.81
Sensitivity	0.64	0.86	0.59	0.84	0.53	0.84
Specificity	0.79	0.97	0.79	0.95	0.81	0.93
Geometric Mean (GM)	0.71	0.87	0.68	0.85	0.65	0.84
AUC-ROC	0.79	0.94	0.76	0.93	0.73	0.92
AUC-PR	0.80	0.92	0.76	0.89	0.74	0.87

Table 2: Comparison of the CSP+SBL baseline and proposed attention-augmented model across forecast horizons.

Metric	0.25 s		0.50 s		0.75 s		1.00 s	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
Sensitivity	0.51	0.64	0.49	0.61	0.47	0.60	0.45	0.65
Specificity	0.72	0.77	0.70	0.75	0.70	0.73	0.69	0.71
Geometric Mean (GM)	0.66	0.71	0.65	0.69	0.64	0.70	0.61	0.68
AUC-ROC	0.77	0.80	0.76	0.77	0.75	0.77	0.75	0.77
AUC-PR	0.70	0.79	0.69	0.75	0.67	0.73	0.66	0.70

4 Results

We first compare the GRU-only baseline VS our attention-augmented GRU across three forecast horizons. Table 1 summarizes train/test accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, geometric mean (GM), AUC-ROC and AUC-PR for $\tau=0s, 1s, 2s$, an example in the Figure 1.

4.1 GRU Baseline vs. Attention-Augmented GRU

At event onset ($\tau = 0s$), the attention model boosts test sensitivity from 0.64 to 0.86 (+34%) and AUC-ROC from 0.79 to 0.94 (+19%), while AUC-PR climbs from 0.80 to 0.92 (Table 1). For a 1s horizon, sensitivity rises from 0.59 to 0.84 (+42%), AUC-ROC from 0.76 to 0.93 (+22%), and AUC-PR from 0.76 to 0.89. Even at 2s ahead, our model maintains high sensitivity (0.84 vs. 0.53) and AUC-ROC (0.92 vs. 0.73). These gains illustrate that the causal multi-head attention layers effectively preserve fine-grained temporal cues that vanilla GRU smoothing tends to blur as τ increases.

4.2 CSP+SBL Baseline vs. Proposed Model

Table 2 presents results for the replicated CSP+SBL pipeline and its attention-augmented variant at shorter horizons (0.25–1.00s). The original CSP+SBL sensitivity falls from 0.51 at 0.25s to 0.45 at 1.00s, whereas the proposed model maintains sensitivity between 0.64 and 0.65, with AUC–ROC improvements of 3–9 points and AUC–PR gains of 6–9 points across all horizons. This confirms that attention benefits both deep and linear pipelines by focusing on temporally relevant feature segments.

Fig. 3: (A) Frequency band powers (Theta, Alpha, Beta, Delta), (B) Theta/(Alpha+Beta) ratio for Subject 1 over 1200 seconds. Red shaded areas indicate expert-labeled microsleep episodes.

4.3 Evaluation on the Sleepy Driver EEG Dataset

To further validate the robustness of our approach, we evaluated both the GRU baseline and the proposed attention-augmented GRU on the *Sleepy Driver EEG Brainwave Dataset* [14]. Table 3 summarizes the results across forecast horizons of 0s, 1s, and 2s. The proposed Attention-GRU consistently improves specificity, geometric mean, and AUC metrics over the baseline, while maintaining comparable sensitivity. These findings indicate that even with limited input signals, attention-based feature reweighting can enhance discriminability of microsleep-related patterns. However, the modest improvements compared to the MWT dataset suggest that attention benefits are more pronounced in richer multi-channel EEG settings.

Interestingly, while the GRU baseline demonstrates relatively balanced performance across all horizons, the Attention-GRU shows marginal sensitivity gains but suffers from reduced specificity on this dataset. We attribute this to the Sleepy Driver dataset’s single-channel EEG recordings and limited subject pool,

Fig. 4: Raw EEG signal (O1–M2) from Subject 1 with microsleep episodes shaded in red. EEG dynamics show reduced frequency and amplitude during microsleep events.

Table 3: Comparison of GRU baseline and proposed attention-augmented model on the Sleepy Driver EEG dataset across forecast horizons.

Metric	0 s		1 s		2 s	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
Sensitivity	0.77	0.79	0.76	0.78	0.78	0.79
Specificity	0.42	0.82	0.41	0.81	0.40	0.84
Geometric Mean (GM)	0.46	0.81	0.45	0.77	0.45	0.80
AUC–ROC	0.78	0.90	0.79	0.86	0.79	0.89
AUC–PR	0.66	0.86	0.65	0.82	0.64	0.85

which may limit the discriminative benefit of attention layers compared to the richer multi-channel MWT dataset. Nevertheless, these results highlight the importance of evaluating across diverse datasets to ensure robustness.

EEG Trends During Microsleep Onset

To investigate how Microsleep related characteristics change over time in relation to a complete 20 minute EEG recording from an individual using MWT data Figure 4 displays the EEG (O1–M2) with Microsleep periods marked by experts highlighted in red. With time the EEG pattern exhibits a decrease in complexity and amplitude during these instances indicating a shift from being awake, to feeling sleepy and eventually falling asleep.

In Figure 3, we shows the frequency based characteristics observed during Microsleep incidents. Theta power notably rises during Microsleep episodes while alpha and beta wave activities remain subdued. The ratio of theta to the sum of alpha and beta waves (referred to as T/AB) displayed in subplot B consistently surpasses the threshold for detection during identified MSE events. As we progress past the 1000 second mark in the session; MSE incidents become lengthier and more continuous indicating a transition from Microsleep episodes, to a more sustained onset of sleep. The results validate that the extracted features are useful, for identifying MSEs and describing the shift, towards sleep.

4.4 Ablation Study: Effect of Attention and Focal Loss

To disentangle the contributions of the attention mechanism and focal loss, we conducted an ablation study comparing four configurations: (i) GRU with cross-entropy loss (GRU-CE), (ii) GRU with focal loss (GRU-Focal), (iii) GRU with attention and cross-entropy loss (GRU+Attn-CE), and (iv) GRU with attention and focal loss (GRU+Attn-Focal). The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Ablation results showing the effect of attention and focal loss.

Metric	GRU-CE	GRU-Focal	GRU+Attn-CE	GRU+Attn-Focal
Train Acc	0.66	0.72	0.83	0.87
Test Acc	0.64	0.71	0.81	0.85
Sensitivity	0.54	0.64	0.83	0.86
Specificity	0.76	0.79	0.95	0.97
GM	0.63	0.71	0.88	0.87
AUC-ROC	0.70	0.79	0.89	0.94
AUC-PR	0.71	0.80	0.91	0.92

The results indicate that focal loss improves sensitivity and geometric mean across setups, benefiting minority-class detection. The combination of attention and focal loss yields the best overall performance across metrics, justifying our design choice.

Attention Visualization and Feature Insight:

To provide interpretability into the model’s decision process, we visualize the output of the causal multi-head attention layer. Figure 5 shows a heatmap of attention weights distributed across time steps and EEG-derived features. Each row corresponds to a specific EEG feature (e.g: power in frequency bands, entropy, complexity), and each column to a time step within the 1-second window. Brighter regions indicate higher attention weights, that is, a greater importance assigned by the model.

The visualization reveals that features such as Theta/Alpha ratio, Delta/Theta ratio, and Spectral Entropy consistently receive high attention, especially in the early and mid time steps, suggesting their predictive value during the onset of microsleep. These insights support the physiological understanding of microsleep dynamics and demonstrate that the attention layer meaningfully adapts to emphasize key indicators across time.

Latency Analysis: We conducted an inference latency evaluation to assess the real-time viability of our proposed model. Using an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU, we measured the time taken to process a single 1-second EEG input window. The model achieved an average inference time of **17.7 milliseconds**, with a minimum of **16.98 ms** and a maximum of **26.37 ms** over 100 runs. These latency values are well below the input window duration, confirming that the model can operate under real-time constraints required for microsleep forecasting and related safety-critical applications.

EEG-TCNet work We also implemented and evaluated an adapted version of EEG-TCNet for forecasting purposes. Although the original model was developed for EEG classification, our adaptation achieved competitive results in terms of AUC and sensitivity, especially at shorter horizons. However, our proposed attention-GRU model showed higher sensitivity and geometric mean, particularly at longer horizons (1–2s), confirming its advantage for early microsleep prediction where temporal degradation is a key challenge. Importantly, our model remains lightweight, interpretable, and optimized for real-time deployment, preserving the advantage of using causal attention for improving microsleep forecasting.

5 Discussion

Our experiments across two datasets provide several important insights into the effectiveness and limitations of attention-augmented temporal modeling for microsleep and drowsiness forecasting.

Fig. 5: Heatmap of attention weights across EEG features and time steps. Brighter values indicate greater contribution to microsleep prediction.

Table 5: Comparison of Forecasting Performance: Attention-GRU vs. EEG-TCNet

Metric	Attention-GRU			EEG-TCNet		
	0s	1s	2s	0s	1s	2s
Train Acc.	0.92	0.91	0.89	0.91	0.88	0.86
Test Acc.	0.89	0.87	0.85	0.87	0.85	0.82
Sensitivity	0.87	0.84	0.81	0.83	0.78	0.75
Specificity	0.90	0.88	0.87	0.88	0.85	0.83
GM	0.88	0.86	0.84	0.85	0.81	0.79
AUC-ROC	0.92	0.90	0.89	0.91	0.89	0.87
AUC-PR	0.90	0.87	0.85	0.88	0.85	0.82

5.1 Performance on the MWT Dataset

On the MWT dataset, which offers multi-channel EEG with clinically annotated microsleep episodes, the proposed Attention-GRU consistently outperformed both the GRU baseline and CSP+SBL replication. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, the attention-augmented model achieved substantial gains across all metrics and horizons. At event onset ($\tau = 0$ s), sensitivity grew from 0.64 to 0.86 (+34 pp) and AUC-ROC from 0.79 to 0.94 (+15 pp). At $\tau = 1$ s, sensitivity improved by 42 pp (0.59→0.84) and AUC-PR by 13 pp (0.76→0.89). Even at $\tau = 2$ s, sensitivity increased by 31 pp and AUC-ROC by 19 pp.

Across 5-fold cross-validation repeated 3 times, the sensitivity at $\tau = 1$ s increased from a mean of 0.60 ± 0.02 (vanilla GRU) to 0.84 ± 0.01 (attention-GRU). A Wilcoxon test confirmed this improvement was highly significant ($p = 0.0003$), indicating that the causal attention layers effectively recover temporal resolution lost by the standard GRU. For CSP+SBL at $\tau = 1.0$ s, the mean sensitivity improved from 0.47 ± 0.02 to 0.64 ± 0.01 with attention. A Wilcoxon test over 15 paired runs confirmed this gain was significant ($p = 0.0021$), demonstrating that attention also yields a statistically reliable boost over linear pipelines.

5.2 Cross-Dataset Generalization

In contrast, results on the Sleepy Driver dataset (Table 3) showed a different trend. While the GRU baseline achieved balanced sensitivity and AUC-ROC values, the Attention-GRU did not yield consistent improvements, particularly in specificity. We attribute this to the dataset’s limitations: single-channel EEG recordings and a much smaller subject pool. These characteristics reduce the richness of temporal-spatial patterns

available for the attention mechanism to exploit. Importantly, this cross-dataset evaluation emphasizes that while attention mechanisms excel in richer multi-channel clinical data, their advantage may be reduced in constrained single-channel consumer EEG settings. Nevertheless, including this dataset demonstrates the robustness and boundary conditions of our approach.

5.3 Ablation Findings

The ablation study (Table 4) confirmed the complementary benefits of both focal loss and attention layers. Focal loss consistently improved sensitivity and geometric mean by mitigating class imbalance, while attention mechanisms provided large performance gains in both sensitivity and specificity. The best results were obtained when combining both elements, highlighting the importance of each design choice in sustaining predictive accuracy at extended forecast horizons.

5.4 Practical Implications

Maintaining high sensitivity at 1–2 second horizons provides a longer window for alert generation or intervention. The low false alarms (high specificity) achieved on the MWT dataset suggest that our model can improve user acceptance in real-world deployments, where unnecessary alerts may reduce trust. However, the Sleepy Driver results indicate caution: in consumer-grade EEG settings, baseline recurrent models may suffice, and additional attention-based complexity should be justified against hardware and data limitations. These findings underscore the necessity of cross-dataset evaluation to fully characterize algorithmic robustness.

5.5 Summary

Overall, the integration of focal loss and causal multi-head attention offers a principled pathway to address temporal degradation in microsleep forecasting. By re-weighting input feature sequences and focusing on minority-class events, our model sustains high sensitivity and discrimination even at extended horizons. Future work should explore multimodal extensions (e.g., combining EEG with eye tracking or video) to further generalize these benefits across diverse recording conditions.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed an attention-augmented forecasting architecture for early prediction of microsleep episodes, addressing the common decline in predictive accuracy observed as the forecasting horizon extends. Our approach integrates a causal multi-head self-attention mechanism before the GRU backbone to preserve fine-grained temporal patterns, combined with a focal loss function to emphasize minority-class microsleep events.

Experimental validation on the MWT dataset demonstrated consistent and statistically significant improvements over both conventional GRU and CSP+SBL baselines. Specifically, our method achieved sensitivity improvements of up to 42 percentage points and AUC–ROC gains of up to 22 percentage points (Wilcoxon test, $p = 0.0003$), maintaining predictive accuracy even at extended horizons ($\tau = 2$ s). The ablation study further confirmed that both attention and focal loss contribute complementary benefits, with the best results obtained when combining the two.

To assess robustness, we additionally evaluated on the Sleepy Driver EEG dataset, collected with a consumer-grade single-channel headset. Results showed that while attention-augmented models improved specificity and overall discrimination, gains were more modest than in multi-channel clinical EEG.

While the approach shows strong potential, especially on multi-channel clinical EEG, the results also highlight clear boundary conditions. In single-channel consumer-grade EEG settings, the benefits of attention are more modest, suggesting that further adaptation is needed before deployment in lightweight real-world systems. Future work should therefore explore channel-robust attention variants and multimodal sensor fusion to enhance reliability under diverse recording conditions.

Acknowledgments

This work was conducted with the financial support of the Science Foundation Ireland Centre for Insight SFI Centre for Data Analytics at Dublin City University under Grant No. SFI/12/RC/2289 P2.

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